

TECHNICAL TRAINING OF THE FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In this article, it is mentioned about the organization and management of the processes of formation of technological skills among elementary school teachers, analysis and improvement based on prioritization of subject relations in pedagogical activities.*

Key words: *gender, temperament, character, mood, mental state, health, anatomical and physiological characteristics, mime and pantomimic skills*

Technical training is a set of general pedagogical knowledge and skills necessary not only in the educational process, but also in the entire professional activity of the future primary school teacher. The important aspects of pedagogical techniques are the professional skills that determine the future teacher's skills, that is, his ability to speak literately and expressively in front of young students, effectively express his opinion and knowledge in understandable language, control his emotions, clear gestures, meaningful such as a look, an encouraging or sarcastic smile, influencing children's minds and thinking through the infinite power of words, being present, and having psychological knowledge.

Characteristics of the acting art, mime and pantomimic skills, play an important role in directing the future teacher's actions in front of the educational objects. If an actor prepares an image in a certain period of time and performs it on stage in the same way one or more times, the teacher prepares in depth for the whole school year, connecting a new topic with the previous topics and conveying it to the minds of students using modern innovative methods. is obliged to perform pedagogical activities taking into account the unique pedagogical and psychological environment and the personal characteristics of each student. In order to carry out such a huge responsibility at a high level, a future primary school teacher is required to have high pedagogical technical training.

The role and importance of future elementary school teachers together with their parents in raising a healthy and perfect generation, which is the dream of the whole nation, has always been recognized. Because the contribution of teachers and coaches is incomparable in making a person mature as a human being, instilling in him the feelings of knowledge and thinking, loyalty to the country, kindness, living with dreams and desires, and in making him a worthy citizen of our society. It is clear to everyone that their success in the field of education is the result of their tireless work. This is reflected in the long, hard work, in the refinement of methods of influence in education and upbringing, in the proper use of various practical tasks, and in the perfect solution of special skills needed in education and extracurricular activities.

Professionals of this profession are well aware of the importance of mastering the speech technique and voice in the pedagogical activities of the future elementary school teacher. The ability of a teacher to speak without mistakes, beautifully and clearly, to polish his speech to be expressive and meaningful, to be able to clearly reflect his opinions, thoughts and feelings in words, to convey gestures and an expressive look to the specified point - is the guarantee of success in professional activity.

Pedagogical technique is a set of skills that enable the future elementary school teacher to see, hear and feel his pupils in his pedagogical activities. The famous pedagogue A.S. Makarenko wrote in his works: "An educator should know how to organize, move smoothly, use humor, joy and anger in their place. When he steps on the educational platform, he should be able to behave in such a way that his every movement, behavior, and dress should educate the children.

Pedagogical scientist Yu.P. Azarov's scientific researches defined pedagogical technique as follows: firstly, developed pedagogical technique helps the teacher to show himself deeper and brighter in his pedagogical activities, to reveal all the good, professionally important aspects of his personality in the relationship with students. Pedagogical technique allows the teacher to save his time and energy for creative activities, frees him from the distraction of finding and using the necessary words in the process of pedagogical communication or explaining the tone caused by inappropriate words. A teacher with perfect pedagogical techniques does not suffer from losing his voice, from being distracted by concerns unrelated to his work. Pedagogical technique helps the teacher to quickly and clearly find the right word, tone, look, gesture, and also in sudden and unexpected pedagogical situations, allows the teacher to quickly and easily get out of conflicts based on the ability to think calmly and analyze with intelligence and understanding creates direct conditions for feeling satisfaction from professional activity.

Secondly, the pedagogical technique also affects the growth of the quality level of the individual. An important feature of pedagogical techniques is that all of them have a clearly expressed individual character, that is, it is formed on the basis of the teacher's psycho-physiological characteristics. Personal pedagogical technique significantly depends on the teacher's age, gender, temperament, character, mood, mental state, health, anatomical and physiological characteristics.

For example, working on expressiveness, cleanliness, error-free speech develops the teacher's thinking at the same time. Possessing the ability to directly control the state of mind leads to the growth of the virtue of self-control, which is recognized as essential to human nature. In addition, all the skills of the teacher in the field of pedagogical techniques are shown at the same time in the process of clear interaction in the pedagogical activity. And self-observation (reflection) makes it possible to successfully choose the means of expression.

Thirdly, in the process of mastering the pedagogical technique, the human feelings and capabilities of the future elementary school teacher as a person, moral and aesthetic aspects, pedagogical tact and delicacy, which reflect the level of general and professional culture, are more fully revealed. In these definitions given by the researcher in relation to the pedagogical technique, it is emphasized how important the pedagogical technique is for the teacher's professional activity. In this classification, it is observed that the relative views of the authors are close to each other in terms of meaning. According to V.P. Galakhova, the perfect classification of "pedagogical skill" should be found in the pedagogical technique of the future teacher. He emphasizes that pedagogical technique means "a set of skills that allow a teacher to express himself more vividly, creatively and perfectly as a person, and to achieve high results in professional pedagogical activity, to convey his thoughts and knowledge to students by heart." Pedagogical technique includes the ability to control one's own behavior and the ability to exert pedagogical influence on a child's personality and a group of children. It can be seen that V.P. Galakhova's definition of pedagogical technique can be included in the class of perfectly given definitions.

Today's elementary school teacher should consider the role of pedagogical technique in the system of pedagogical skills to be incomparable. Because it explains to the teacher how to correctly control his body movements (mimicry, pantomime), control his feelings (emotions), acquire enthusiasm, abilities, speech techniques and use them in educational activities, extracurricular educational and educational activities.

Conclusion

Therefore, the pedagogical technique is a collection of such professional and personal skills in the teacher's professional activity that it affects the teacher's pedagogical activity, serves as the main guide in the organization and management of the educational process.

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